

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND INVITRO CHARACTERIZATION OF
IVACAFTOR SOLID DISPERSION TABLETS**Pooja Macharla*¹, Aukunuru Jitha^{1,2}¹Department Of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy, Telangana, India., ²Technology Consultants, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Article Received: August 2024

Accepted: September 2024

Published: October 2024

Abstract:

Ivacaftor is a cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator to treat and prevent certain types of serious, life-threatening ventricular arrhythmias. It is an BCS class-II drug having higher half-life. To improve the biological performance of Ivacaftor solid dispersion with oral disintegrating tablet was formulated by using SSG, Soluplus and PVP K-30. Solid dispersions of Ivacaftor were prepared with different carriers in different ratios of drug and carrier (1:1, 1:2, 1:3 & 1:4). Results of prepared solid dispersions of Ivacaftor by solvent evaporation method were discussed which includes solubility, melting point determination, drug content uniformity, and invitro dissolution studies. Characterization in solid state was done by various analytical techniques such as FT-IR studies. Finally by comparing all the formulations, formulation (F12) containing Ivacaftor + PVP K30 (1:4) shows better results by solvent evaporation method at the end of 60 min with maximum drug release, hence it was selected as the best formulation. From the optimized formulation the Fast dissolving tablets were formulated using different disintegrants in different concentrations. The pre compression and post compression parameters were studied and the results were given. All the results are in the acceptable limit. The in vitro drug release of the formulated tablets were performed using 6.8 pH Phosphate buffer. F12T12 formulation containing Crospovidone shows 98.21% drug release in 30 mins. The optimized formulation follows First order release kinetics.

Keywords: *Ivacaftor, Crospovidone, PVP K30 & FTIR.***Corresponding author:****Pooja Macharla,**Department of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy,
Edulabad, Telangana. Email Id-poojamacharla1605@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Pooja Macharla et al Formulation And Invitro Characterization Of Ivacaftor Solid Dispersion Tablets .., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).**

INTRODUCTION:

Oral bioavailability of a drug depends on its solubility and/or dissolution rate, and dissolution may be the rate determining step for the onset of therapeutic activity. Therefore efforts to increase drug dissolution of drug are often needed. Methods available to improve dissolution include salt formation, micronization and addition of solvent or surface active agents. Solid dispersion (SD) is one of such methods and it involves a dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inner carrier or matrix in solid state prepared by melting, dissolution in solvent or melting-solvent method.

The enhancements of oral bioavailability of such poorly water-soluble drugs often show poor bioavailability because of low and erratic levels of absorption. Drugs that undergo dissolution rate limited gastrointestinal absorption generally show improved dissolution and bio availability as a result of reduction in particle size. However, micronizing of drugs often leads to aggregation and agglomeration of particles, which results in poor wettability. Solid dispersions of poorly water-soluble drugs with water-soluble carriers have been reduced the incidence of these problems and enhanced dissolution. The development of solid dispersions as a practically viable method to enhance bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs overcame the limitations of previous approaches such as salt formation, solubilization by cosolvents, and particle size reduction. Studies revealed that drugs in solid dispersion need not necessarily exist in the micronized state. A fraction of the drug might molecularly disperse in the matrix, thereby forming a solid dispersion. When the solid dispersion is exposed to aqueous media, the carrier dissolves and the drug releases as fine colloidal particles.

Oral bioavailability of a drug depends on its solubility and/or dissolution rate, and dissolution may be the rate determining step for the onset of therapeutic activity. Therefore efforts to increase drug dissolution of drug are often needed. Methods available to improve dissolution include salt formation, micronization and addition of solvent or surface active agents. Solid dispersion (SD) is one of such methods and it involves a dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inner carrier or matrix in solid state prepared by melting, dissolution in solvent or melting-solvent method⁴. The technique has been used for a wide variety of poorly aqueous soluble drug. Poorly soluble drugs represent a problem for their scarce availability related to their low dissolution rate. The major drawback of low aqueous solubility is delays its absorption from the gastrointestinal tract. Solubility

behavior of a drug is one of the key determinants of its oral bioavailability. Noyesh- Whitney equation provides some hints as to how the dissolution rate of even very poorly soluble compounds might be improved to minimize the limitations to oral availability [2].

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = \frac{AD(Cs - c)}{h}$$

Where,

dC/dt - is the rate of dissolution,

A - is the surface area available for dissolution,

D - is the diffusion coefficient of the compound,

Cs - is the solubility of the compound in the dissolution medium,

C - is the concentration of drug in the medium at time **t** and

h - is the thickness of the diffusion boundary layer adjacent to the surface of the dissolving compound. To increase the dissolution rate from equation the following approaches are available.

- To increase the surface area available for dissolution Decreasing the particle size of drug.
- Optimizing the wetting characteristics of compound surface.
- To decrease the boundary layer thickness.
- Ensure sink condition for dissolution.
- Improve apparent solubility of drug under physiologically relevant conditions.
- Drug administered in fed state is a way to improve the dissolution rate.

Solid dispersions:

Solid dispersions (SDs) traditionally have been used as an effective method to improve the dissolution properties and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs. Since 1961, many investigators have studied SDs of poorly water-soluble drugs with various pharmacologically inert carriers to increase the dissolution and oral absorption of poorly water-soluble drug show ever, only a few systems are useful commercially.

Fast or immediate drug dissolution from solid dispersions has been observed due to increased wettability, improved dispersibility of drug particles, existence of the drug in amorphous form with improved solubility and absence of aggregation of drug particles. Literature shows that the solvent evaporation method has been used for the preparation of solid dispersions for dissolution enhancement. Earlier studies show that solid dispersion systems increased the drug dissolution due to improved solubility, wettability and dispersibility using hydrophilic carriers. In the present work, physical mixtures, co-grinding and co-precipitation or solvent

evaporation method was used to prepare solid dispersions of prednisolone. This method requires the minimal amount of solvent in dissolving the drug. We used various polymeric carriers in this study. Polyvinylpyrrolidone(PVP)and poly ethylene glycol (PEG)were chosen as water-soluble polymers.

Classification of solid dispersion:

Eutectic mixtures:

A simple eutectic mixture consists of two compounds which are completely miscible in the liquid state but only to a very limited extent in the solid state. It is prepared by rapid solidification of fused melt of two components that show complete liquid miscibility but negligible solid-solid solution [13].

Amorphous precipitation in crystalline matrix:

This is similar to simple eutectic mixtures but only difference is that drug is precipitated out in an amorphous form [14].

Solid solution: Solid solutions are comparable to liquid solutions, consisting of just one phase irrespective of the number of components. In the case of solid solutions, the drug's particle size has been reduced to its absolute minimum viz. the molecular dimensions¹⁴ and the dissolution rate is determined by the dissolution rate of the carrier. Classified according to their miscibility (continuous versus discontinuous solid solutions) or second, according to the way in which the solvate molecules are distributed in the solvendum (substitutional, interstitial or amorphous) [15].

Continuous solid solutions:

In a continuous solid solution, the components are miscible in all proportions. Theoretically, this means that the bonding strength between the two components is stronger than the bonding strength between the molecules of each of the individual components. Solid solutions of this type have not been reported in the pharmaceutical world till date [16].

Discontinuous solid solutions:

In the case of discontinuous solid solutions, the solubility of each of the components in the other component is limited. Due to practical considerations it has been suggested by Goldberg et al.¹⁴ that the term 'solid solution' should only be applied when the mutual solubility of the two components exceeds 5%.

Substitutional solid dispersions:

Substitution is only possible when the size of the solute molecules differs by less than 15% or so from that of the solvent molecules¹⁵. Classical solid

solutions have crystalline structure, in which the solute molecules can either substitute for solvent molecules in the crystal lattice or fit into the intrsticies between the solvent molecule.

Interstitial solid solutions:

In interstitial solid solutions, the dissolved molecules occupy the interstitial spaces between the solvent molecules in the crystal lattice. Solute molecule diameter should be less than 0.59 times than that of solvent molecular diameter.

Glass solution and suspensions:

Glass solutions are homogeneous glassy system in which solute dissolves in glass carrier. Glass suspensions are mixture in which precipitated particles are suspended in glass solvent. Lattice energy is much lower in glass solution and suspension.

MATERIALS:

IVACAFTOR-

B.M.R.Chemicals,Hyderabad,Soluplus-S.D FINE CHEMICALS, PVP K30-S.D FINE CHEMICALS, SSG-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, Lycoat -B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, Ludiflash-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, Crospovidone-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, MCC-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad,Aspartame-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, Mg. stearate-B.M.R. Chemicals, Hyderabad, Talc-B.M.R. Chemicals,Hyderabad.

METHODOLOGY:

Preformulation studies:

Preformulation testing is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms of a drug substance.

Definition: It can be defined as an investigation of physical and chemical properties of a drug substance alone and when combined with excipients.

Objective: Overall objective of preformulation testing is to generate information useful to the formulator in developingstable and bio-available dosage forms.

The following preformulation studies were carried out for Ivacaftor

- a) Solubility studies
- b) Drug–excipient compatibility studies

a) Solubility studies:

Solubility of Ivacaftor was carried out in different buffers. Saturated solutions were prepared by adding excess drug to the vehicles and shaking on the shaker for 24 hrs at 25°C under constant vibration. Filtered

samples (1ml) were diluted appropriately with suitable buffer and solubility of Ivacaftor was determined spectrophotometrically at 255 nm

b) Drug-polymer compatibility studies

In the preparation of tablet formulation, drug and polymer may interact as they are in close contact with each other, which could lead to the instability of drug. Preformulation studies regarding the drug-polymer interaction are therefore very critical in selecting appropriate polymers. FT-IR spectroscopy was employed to ascertain the compatibility between Ivacaftor, and the selected polymers. The pure drug and drug with excipient were scanned separately.

FT-IR studies:

Sample/KBr ratio:

The concentration of the sample in KBr should be in the range of 0.2% to 1%. The pellet is much thicker than a liquid film, hence a lower concentration in the sample is required (Beer's Law). Too high a concentration usually causes difficulties obtaining clear pellets. The IR beam is absorbed completely, or scattered from the sample which results in very noisy spectra.

Sample preparation:

Completely dried potassium bromide was transferred into a mortar. About 2 % of drug sample was weighed in digital balance, mixed and grind to a fine powder. Two stainless steel disks were taken out of the desiccator. A piece of the pre-cut cardboard (in the tin can next to the oven) on top of one disk was placed and cutout hole was filled with the finely ground mixture. The second stainless steel disk was kept on top and transfers the sandwich onto the pistil in the hydraulic press. With a pumping movement, hydraulic pump handle moved downward. The pistil will start to move upward until it reaches the top of the pump chamber. Then, the pump handle moved upwards and continued pumping until the pressure reaches 20,000 prf. Rest for a few seconds and with the small lever on the left side, the pressure was released. Removing of the disks and pulling apart. Obtained film was homogenous and transparent in appearance. Than inserted into the IR sample holder and attach with scotch tape and run the spectrum.

The physical mixtures of drugs were prepared in 1:1 ratio and then passed through sieve # 30. Samples of drug and excipients were placed in vial, closed and labelled.

Analytical method development by U.V. Spectroscopy:

UV-Visible spectrophotometry is one of the most

frequently employed technique in pharmaceutical analysis. It involves measuring the amount of ultraviolet or visible radiation absorbed by a substance in solution. Instrument which measure the ratio, or function of ratio, of the intensity of two beams of light in the U.V-Visible region are called Ultraviolet-Visible spectrophotometers. In qualitative analysis, organic compounds can be identified by use of spectrophotometer, if any recorded data is available, and quantitative spectrophotometric analysis is used to ascertain the quantity of molecular species absorbing the radiation. Spectrophotometric technique is simple, rapid, moderately specific and applicable to small quantities of compounds. The fundamental law that governs the quantitative spectrophotometric analysis is the Beer -Lambert law.

Scanning of λ_{max} of Ivacaftor:

Preparation of Stock Solution: 10 mg of Ivacaftor was taken in a 10ml volumetric flask. To that 2ml of methanol was added and shaken well to dissolve the drug. The solution was made up to the mark with 6.8pH phosphate buffer to give 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration. From the above solution 1ml is diluted to 10ml with 6.8pH phosphate buffer to give 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration. From the above solution, take 1ml, and diluted to 10ml with 6.8pH phosphate buffer, to give 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration. The prepared solution i.e., 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration was scanned for λ_{max} from 200-400 nm in UV/Visible spectrophotometer.

Calibration curve of Ivacaftor in 6.8pH phosphate buffer:

10mg of Ivacaftor was accurately weighed and transferred into 10ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved and diluted to volume with 6.8pH phosphate buffer to give stock solution containing 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The standard stock solution was then serially diluted with 6.8pH phosphate buffer to get 2 to 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of. The absorbance of the solution was measured against 6.8pH phosphate buffer as blank at 255 nm using UV spectrophotometer. The absorbance values were plotted against concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) to obtain the standard calibration curve.

PREPARATION OF SOLID DISPERSIONS OF IVACAFTOR: [70]

There are several carriers, which have been reported for the preparation of solid dispersions by using Soluplus, PVP K30 and SSG various methods of preparation.

Solvent evaporation method: Solvent evaporation involves emulsification of polymer in aqueous phase and dispersion in a volatile solvent. Then the solvent

is evaporated using high temperature, vacuum, or by continuous stirring or the solvent was then rapidly evaporated with the aid of mild heat (up to about 50 °C) and surface airflow with constant vigorous stirring to form a uniform solid mass.

In solvent evaporation method, the drug and carriers were mixed in 1:1,1:2 ,1:3 & 1:4 ratios in methanol. Solvent was removed by evaporation under reduced pressure. The mass was pulverised and passed through sieve# 60. And now the obtained product was collected.

Solid Dispersions:

Formulation Code	Drug and Polymers Ratio
F1	1:1 (Ivacaftor: SSG)
F2	1:2(Ivacaftor: SSG)
F3	1:3(Ivacaftor: SSG)
F4	1:4(Ivacaftor: SSG)
F5	1:1(Ivacaftor: Soluplus)
F6	1:2(Ivacaftor: Soluplus)
F7	1:3(Ivacaftor: Soluplus)
F8	1:4(Ivacaftor: Soluplus)
F9	1:1(Ivacaftor: PVP K30)
F10	1:2(Ivacaftor: PVP K30)
F11	1:3(Ivacaftor: PVP K30)
F12	1:4(Ivacaftor: PVP K30)

FORMULATION OF IVACAFTOR TABLETS: [75]

Equivalent weight of Ivacaftor was added with suitable excipients and the tablets were formulated by direct compression according to the formulae given in the table. All the ingredients were passed through # 40 mesh sieve separately. The drug and MCC were mixed by adding small portion of each at a time and blending it to get a uniform mixture and kept aside.

Then the other ingredients were mixed in geometrical order and passed through coarse sieve (#40 mesh) and the tablets were compressed using hydraulic press. Compression force of the machine was adjusted to obtain the hardness in the range of 3-4 kg/cm² for all batches. The weight of the tablets was kept constant for all formulations F12T1 to F12T12.

Table.No.6.6: Formulation of Ivacaftor Tablets

Ingredients (mg)	F12 T1	F12 T2	F12 T3	F12 T4	F12 T5	F12 T6	F12 T7	F12 T8	F12 T9	F12 T10	F12 T11	F12 T12
Ivacaftor (weight equivalent to 150 mg)	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
Lycoat	15	30	45	60	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Ludiflash	--	--	--	--	15	30	45	60	--	--	--	--
Crospovidone	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	30	45	60
MCC	171	156	141	126	171	156	141	126	171	156	141	126
Aspartame	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Mg. stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Solubility:**

Solubility of was carried out at 25°C using 0.1 N HCL, 6.8 phosphate buffer, 7.4 pH buffer , methanol and ethanol.

Table.No.7.1.: Solubility studies data of Ivacaftor

MEDIUM	SOLUBILITY (mg/ml)
6.8 pH phosphate buffer	1.248
7.4 pH phosphate buffer	0.763
0.1 N HCL	0.426

Fig.No.7.1: Graphical representation of Ivacaftor Solubility studies**Discussion:**

From the above conducted solubility studies in various buffers we can say that 6.8 pH Phosphate buffer solution has more solubility when compared to other buffer solutions.

Analytical method development by U.V. Spectroscopy:**Uv Scan Spectrum of Ivacaftor :**

Fig.No.7.2. Uv Scan Spectrum of Ivacaftor

Discussion:

A solution of Ivacaftor containing the conc. 10 µg/ ml was prepared in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer and UV spectrum was taken using Single Beam Spectrophotometer (YIS-294). The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400 nm. The maximum absorbance was found to be at 255 nm.

Calibration curve of Ivacaftor in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer:

Table.No.7.2. Calibration curve of Ivacaftor in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.134
4	0.283
6	0.426
8	0.569
10	0.697
12	0.837

Fig.No.7.3. Calibration curve of Ivacaftor

Discussion:

Calibration curve of Ivacaftor was constructed in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer at maximum wavelength of 255 nm and analyzed for regression analysis. Regression analysis was selected because it minimizes the deviation and correct the variance heterogeneity. The regression line was defined by its slope (m) and its intercept (C) for normal regression analysis was found as 0.0701 and 0.0005, with regression coefficient of 0.9997 respectively.

Drug excipient compatibility: Drug and excipient compatibility was confirmed by comparing spectra of FT-IR analysis of pure drug with that of various excipients used in the formulation.

Fig.No.7.4.IR spectrum of pure Ivacaftor

Fig.No.7.5.IR spectrum of Ivacaftor Optimised Formulation

Discussion: From the drug excipient compatibility studies we observe that there are no interactions between the pure drug (Ivacaftor) and optimized formulation (Ivacaftor: excipients) which indicates there are no physical changes.

Drug Content Of Solid Dispersions :**Table.No.7.4: Drug content of solid dispersions**

Formulation code	%Drug content
F1	90.47%
F2	91.35%
F3	93.19%
F4	94.25%
F5	92.46%
F6	94.18%
F7	95.21%
F8	96.19%
F9	93.37%
F10	94.42%
F11	96.19%
F12	98.48%

Discussion: The Drug content of the formulated solid dispersions was found to be in the range of 90.47%- 98.48% respectively.

Percentage Yield of Solid Dispersions:**Table.No.7.3: Percentage yield of solid dispersions**

Formulation code	Percentage yield
F1	92.18%
F2	93.24%
F3	95.46%
F4	96.29%
F5	88.48%
F6	90.25%
F7	92.43%
F8	94.28%
F9	93.45%
F10	95.19%
F11	97.26%
F12	99.48%

Discussion: The Percentage yield of the formulated solid dispersions was found to be in the range of 88.48%- 99.48% respectively.

Invitro drug release studies of solid dispersions:**Table.No7.5: *Invitro* drug release studies for formulations (F1-F12)**

Time (Min)	Percentage drug release											
	Ivacaftor : SSG				Ivacaftor : Soluplus				Ivacaftor : PVP K30			
	1:1 (F1)	1:2 (F2)	1:3 (F3)	1:4 (F4)	1:1 (F5)	1:2 (F6)	1:3 (F7)	1:4 (F8)	1:1 (F9)	1:2 (F10)	1:3 (F11)	1:4 (F12)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	46.16	50.26	53.64	55.24	48.16	53.26	54.64	57.24	51.16	55.26	57.64	60.24
10	57.24	61.63	64.35	67.24	59.24	65.63	67.35	69.24	60.24	66.63	68.35	76.24
15	65.43	70.98	71.03	73.45	67.43	73.98	78.03	76.45	68.43	77.98	79.03	80.45
30	79.29	78.09	79.32	82.25	81.29	82.09	85.32	85.25	83.29	86.09	87.32	89.25
45	84.49	87.32	88.56	88.29	87.49	89.32	90.56	91.29	88.49	92.32	91.56	94.29
60	89.37	91.42	93.11	95.34	91.37	92.42	93.11	96.34	92.37	94.42	96.11	98.34

Discussion:

In-vitro drug release of Ivacaftor solid dispersions with SSG in various ratios were observed which shows at the end of 60 mins, the formulation F1 releases 89.37%, formulation F2 releases 91.42%, F3 releases 93.11% and F4 releases 95.34%, while Soluplus used as carrier shows formulation F5 releases 91.37%, formulation F6 releases 92.42%, and formulation F7 releases 93.11% and F8 release 96.34% while PVP K30 used as carrier shows formulation F9 releases 92.37%, formulation F10 releases 94.42%, formulation F11 releases 96.11% and formulation F12 releases 98.34% at the end 60 minutes.

Among all formulation F12 formulation shows maximum drug release at the end of 60 minutes so it was chosen as optimized formulation.

In-vitro* drug release kinetics studies for best formulation F12:*Discussion:**

By comparing the release kinetics studies of best formulation with zero order and first order we can say that the best formulation follows first order release kinetics studies having R^2 value 0.985 were as zero order release kinetics studies having R^2 value 0.645, hence we can say that the best formulation follows first order release kinetics.

Evaluation of Ivacaftor Fast disintegrating Tablets:

Table.No7.6 : Pre Compression parameters

Formulation Code	Derived properties		Flow properties		
	Bulk density (mean±SD) g/cm ³	Tapped density (mean±SD) g/cm ³	Angle of Repose ^o (mean±SD)	Carr's index (mean±SD) %	Hausner's ratio (mean±SD)
F12T1	0.328	0.412	24.21	17.24	1.16
F12T2	0.342	0.429	25.24	15.26	1.15
F12T3	0.353	0.434	27.48	14.48	1.14
F12T4	0.367	0.449	28.36	13.25	1.13
F12T5	0.335	0.421	22.87	18.46	1.19
F12T6	0.346	0.428	24.45	16.18	1.17
F12T7	0.358	0.437	25.26	15.34	1.16
F12T8	0.373	0.343	26.41	14.25	1.14
F12T9	0.356	0.442	25.76	14.46	1.15
F12T10	0.367	0.458	27.25	13.19	1.14
F12T11	0.375	0.464	28.46	12.37	1.13
F12T12	0.384	0.479	29.28	11.45	1.10

Discussion:

The angle of repose of different formulations was ≤ 29.28 which indicates that material had good flow property. So, it was confirmed that the flow property of blends were free flowing. The bulk density of blend was found between 0.328g/cm³ to 0.384g/cm³. Tapped density was found between 0.412g/cm³ to 0.479g/cm³. These values indicate that the blends had good flow property. Carr's index for all the formulations was found to be between 11.45%-18.46% and Hausner's ratio from 1.10-1.19, which reveals that the blends have good flow character.

Characterization of tablets:**Post Compression parameters:**

All the batches of tablet formulations were characterized for official evaluation parameters like Weight variation, Hardness, Friability, Tablet thickness and drug content and results are shown in the table

Table.No 7.7 : Characterization Ivacaftor Fast disintegrating tablets

Formulation	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Hardness (kp)	Friability (%)	Disintegrating time(sec)
F12T1	500.21	4.21	8.21	5.3	0.75	23
F12T2	502.18	4.24	8.24	6.4	0.68	20
F12T3	501.26	4.20	8.26	6.8	0.57	18
F12T4	499.42	4.19	8.27	7.6	0.54	16
F12T5	500.29	4.20	8.24	4.3	0.65	21
F12T6	200.37	4.22	8.26	5.6	0.51	17
F12T7	499.42	4.23	8.28	6.7	0.49	15
F12T8	502.15	4.24	8.29	7.8	0.42	14
F12T9	501.39	4.25	8.26	5.4	0.58	18
F12T10	498.21	4.21	8.28	6.3	0.46	16
F12T11	501.45	4.24	8.30	7.2	0.37	14
F12T12	500.10	4.26	8.32	8.5	0.31	12

Discussion:

Hardness of the tablet was acceptable and uniform from batch to batch variation, which was found to be 5.3 – 8.5 kg/cm². All the formulations passed the weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the pharmacopoeial limits of the tablet weight. Friability values were found to be less than 1% in all the formulations F12T1 – F12T12 and considered to be satisfactory ensuring that all the formulations are mechanically stable.

Drug Content of tablets:

Formulation code	Drug content (%)
F12T1	94.37%
F12T2	96.21%
F12T3	97.43%
F12T4	98.21%
F12T5	99.37%
F12T6	95.21%
F12T7	96.34%
F12T8	98.46%
F12T9	96.37%
F12T10	97.48%
F12T11	98.26%
F12T12	99.43%

Discussion:

The drug content values for all the formulations (F12T1 – F12T12) was found to be in the range of 94.37%-99.43%.

Dissolution studies of the tablets:

The prepared tablets were subjected to dissolution studies in order to know the amount drug release.

Table. No. 7.8 :% Cumulative drug release of formulations F12T1 – F12T6

Time(min)	F12T1	F12T2	F12T3	F12T4	F12T5	F12T6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	57.38	60.27	67.24	87.47	53.21	58.67
10	68.06	75.34	82.38	88.38	64.24	71.35
15	73.24	78.46	88.28	94.48	70.36	75.48
20	78.15	85.28	94.45	97.37	77.48	82.35
25	89.54	93.19	98.26		85.25	90.28
30	96.85	98.35			94.37	97.38

Table. No. 7.9 :% Cumulative drug release of formulations F12T7 – F12T12

Time(min)	F12T7	F12T8	F12T9	F12T10	F12T11	F12T12
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	62.24	75.47	62.21	67.45	76.54	88.47
10	75.38	86.38	72.46	76.38	83.58	90.38
15	84.28	91.48	79.22	82.14	89.68	95.48
20	90.45	97.25	85.19	89.24	95.45	98.21
25	97.26		90.34	94.35	98.78	
30			97.25	98.67		

IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE OF F12T9 -F12T12**Fig.No.7.15: in vitro drug release of formulations F12T9 -F12T12**

Discussion:

The formulations containing CCS as a super disintegrant in different concentrations like 15, 30, 45 and 60mg reveals that the increased in the super disintegrant concentration decreases the drug release time and the F12T12 formulation containing CCS 60mg shows maximum amount of drug release (98.21%) at the end of 20mins.

Drug release kinetics:**Zero order plot of (f12t12):**

Fig.No.7.16.:ZERO ORDER PLOT OF (F12T12)

First order plot of (f12t12):

Fig.No.7.17:FIRST ORDER PLOT OF (F12T12)

Order of kinetics	Zero Order	First Order
Regression values	0.591	0.905

DISCUSSION:

The drug release from the tablets was explained by using mathematical model equations such as zero

order, first order methods. Based on the regression values it was concluded that the optimized formulation **F12T12** follows First order kinetics.

SUMMARY:

The therapeutic efficacy of a drug product intended to be administered by the oral route depends on its absorption by the gastro-intestinal tract. It is well established that dissolution is frequently the rate-limiting step in the gastro intestinal absorption of a drug from a solid dosage form. Poorly soluble drugs have been shown to be unpredictable and are slowly absorbed as compared with drugs with higher solubility. Consequently, these drugs present great challenges to further development into bioavailable dosage forms. Hence it is important to enhance the aqueous solubility, dissolution rate and bioavailability of these drugs from its oral solid dosage forms. Solid dispersion technique by mannitol, Croscopovidone & SSG have been used to improve the dissolution properties and bioavailability of poorly water- soluble drugs. This study has demonstrated the possibility of markedly improving the dissolution performance of Ivacaftor by solid dispersion technique.

Ivacaftor is cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator and it is an BCS class II drug having absolute bioavailability of Ivacaftor is low.

Therefore, a favourable formulation which can enhance solubility and dissolution rate of this model drug may help effectively. Thus, studies were carried out to improve the solubility and hence dissolution rate, efficiency and bioavailability of poorly soluble drug Ivacaftor through solid dispersion technique using SSG, Soluplus and PVP K30.

The brief introduction about solid dispersions were explained in the introduction part. Further more, in this chapter introduction on dissolution rate and various approaches to improve the solubility; particularly on solid dispersion technology was elaborated. The aim and objective was also discussed.

Drug profile and excipient profiles were included with complete drug description of Ivacaftor and outlined their usage, contraindication and side effects.

Literature survey related to preparation and past research work on solid dispersions with various drugs and also by different methods.

Methodology as well as materials used and experimental methods employed in the present investigation were explained in detail. Later introduction regarding all the evaluation parameters

and method of preparation of physical mixtures and solid dispersions of Ivacaftor by solvent evaporation was explained. Solid dispersions of Ivacaftor were prepared with different carriers in different ratios of drug and carrier(1:1, 1:2,1:3&1:4).

Results of prepared solid dispersions of Ivacaftor by solvent evaporation method were discussed which includes solubility, melting point determination, drug content uniformity, entrapment efficiency and *invitro* dissolution studies. Characterization in solid state was done by various analytical techniques such as FT-IR studies.

Finally by comparing all the formulations (F1-F12) formulation (F3) containing Ivacaftor+ PVP K30 (1:4) shows better results by solvent evaporation method at the end of 60 min with drug release of 98.34%, hence it was selected as the best formulation.

From the optimized formulation the FDT tablets were formulated using different disintegrants in different concentrations.

The pre compression and post compression parameters were studied and the results were given. all the results are in the acceptable limit.

The in vitro drug release of the formulated tablets were performed using 6.8 pH Phosphate Buffer.

The formulation F12T12 containing 60mg Croscopovidone shows 98.21% drug release in 30mins. The optimized formulation follows first order release kinetics.

CONCLUSION:

Croscopovidone and Mannitol was used in the preparation of solid dispersions by solvent evaporation method. By observing the dissolution studies the Ivacaftor with Croscopovidone (1:3).shows better drug release. And all the prepared solid dispersions were evaluated and results was explained in above mentioned data.

The following conclusions were drawn from the present investigations.

- From the Solubility studies in various buffers we can say that 0.1N HCL buffer has more solubility when compared to other buffer solutions for Ivacaftor.
- Form the drug excipient compatibility studies we observe that there are no interactions between the pure drug and optimized formulation (drug + excipients) which indicates there are no physical changes.

- All the formulations of Ivacaftor were prepared solvent evaporation method
- All the prepared solid dispersions were evaluated for drug content
- The invitro dissolution studies of Ivacaftor was performed.
- From the optimized formulation of the solid dispersions(i.e.,F12) weight equivalent of Ivacaftor was used along with the super disintegrant like Crospovidone.
- Pre compression and Post compression evaluation studies were performed.
- The F12T12 better drug release with 60mg Crospovidone up to 98.21% of drug release at the end of 30mins.
- Drug release kinetics of the optimized formulation shows First order drug release.

REFERENCES:

1. Noyes, A.A., and Whitney W.R., (1897). The rate of solution of solid substances in their own solutions, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 19: 930-934.
2. Van Drooge, D.J. et al. (2006). Characterization of the molecular distribution of drugs in glassy solid dispersions at the nano-meter scale, using differential scanning calorimetry and gravimetric water vapour sorption techniques. *Int. J. Pharm.*, 310: 220–229.
3. Galia, E., Nicolaidis, E., Hoërter, D., LoÈbenberg, R., Reppas, C., and Dressman, J.B., (1998). Evaluation of various dissolution media for predicting in vivo performance of class I and II drugs. *Pharm. Res.*, 15: 698-705.
4. Sengodan guruswamy, V., and Mishra, D.N., 2006. Preparation and evaluation of solid dispersion of meloxicam with skimmed milk. *The Pharmaceutic. Soc. Jap.*, 126(2): 93-97.
5. Hancock, B.C., and Zogra, G., (1997). Characteristics and significance of the amorphous state in pharmaceutical systems (review). *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 86: 1-12.
6. Hoerter, D., and Dressman, J.B., (1997). Influence of physicochemical properties on dissolution of drugs in the gastrointestinal tract (review). *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.*, 25-14.
7. Loftsson, T., and Brewster, M.E., (1996). Pharmaceutical application of cyclodextrins. 1. Drug solubilisation and stabilization (review). *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 85: 1010-1025.
8. Sekiguchi, K., and Obi, N., (1961). Studies on absorption of eutectic mixtures. I. A comparison of the behavior of eutectic mixtures of sulphathiazole and that of ordinary sulphathiazole in man. *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 9: 866-872.
9. Taylor, L.S., and Zogra, G., (1997). Spectroscopic characterization of interactions between PVP and indomethacin in amorphous molecular dispersions. *Pharm. Res.*, 14: 1691-1698.
10. Goldberg, A.H., Gibaldi, M., and Kanig, J.L., (1966). Increasing dissolution rates and gastrointestinal absorption of drugs via solid solutions and eutectic mixtures II ± experimental evaluation of a eutectic mixture: urea±acetaminophen system. *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 55: 482-487.
11. Chiou, W.L., and Rielman, S., (1971). Pharmaceutical application of solid dispersion system. *J.Pharm.Sci.*, 60: 1281-1302.
12. Goldberg, A.H., Gibaldi, M., and Kanig, J.L., (1965). Increasing dissolution rates and gastrointestinal absorption of drugs via solid solutions and eutectic mixtures I theoretical considerations and discussion of the literature. *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 54: 1145-1148.
13. Kreuter, J., Kreuter, J., and Herzfeldt, C.D., (1999). *Grundlagen der Arznei-formenlehre Galenik, 2*, Springer, Frankfurt am Main. 262-274.
14. Chiou, W.L., and Riegelman, S., (1969). Preparation and dissolution characteristics of several fast-release solid dispersions of griseofulvin. *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 58: 1505-1510.
15. Vasconcelos, T.F., Sarmento, B., and Costa, P., (2007). Solid dispersions as strategy to improve oral bioavailability of poor water soluble drugs. *Drug discovery today.*, 12: 1069-1070.